

A high pressure pathway toward boron-based nanostructured solids†

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Inorganic nanocomposites made of an inorganic matrix containing nanoparticle inclusions provide materials of advanced mechanical, magnetic, electrical properties and multifunctionality. The range of compounds that can be implemented in nanocomposites is still narrow and new preparation methods are required to design such advanced materials. Herein, we describe how the combination of nanocrystal synthesis in molten salts with subsequent heat treatment at a pressure in the GPa range gives access to a new family of boron-based nanocomposites. With the case studies of HfB₂/β-HfB₂O₅ and CaB₆/CaB₂O_{4(IV)}, we demonstrate by X-ray diffraction and through (scanning) transmission electron microscopy the crystallization of borate matrices into rare compounds and unique nanostructured solids, while metal boride nanocrystals remain dispersed in the matrix and maintain small sizes below 30 nm, thus demonstrating a new multidisciplinary approach toward nanoscaled heterostructures.

Introduction

Inorganic nanocomposites are made of an inorganic matrix that contains nanoparticle inclusions to target the original mechanical, magnetic, electrical properties and multi-functionality.^{1–5} The production methods known to yield ceramic matrix nanocomposites consist mostly of two approaches: either embedding preformed nanoparticles into

matrices, or precipitating the inclusions directly in the matrix.^{2,3} These techniques are restricted to simple oxide and nitride matrices. To push further the opportunities given by these complex systems, the range of compounds to be implemented in nanocomposites must be widened. We present herein a third route based on the crystallization of the matrix around nanoparticles under extreme conditions, in order to combine crystalline matrices and nanoparticles of rare structures and compounds.

High pressures and temperatures (HP–HT) ranging from 1 to 20 GPa and from 500 to 1500 °C are a realm of opportunities to synthesize crystalline materials not reachable at pressures close to the atmospheric one.^{6–9} Such HP–HT ranges are compatible with large scale industrial production.¹⁰ But to yield nanocomposites, nanoscaled inclusions should survive such extreme conditions, thus questioning the behavior of nano-structured materials under HP–HT treatment.

The current HP studies on nanoparticles deal with two families of solids: (1) metal oxides by applying HP only and no heating,^{11–14} (2) light element B, C, or N-based non-oxides that crystallize only under both HP and HT.^{7,15–17} In the latter case, nanostructuring increases hardness toward ultrahard materials (e.g. nanostructured diamond or c-BN).^{7,17–24} Overall, all previous studies on nanostructured materials under extreme conditions focused on single phase systems, phases that could be obtained at room pressure, or nanocomposites made of well-known high pressure solid state phases. A new preparation method of nanocomposites with high control over the size and the composition of the nano-inclusions, and which could provide access to complex solids, would provide new perspectives for the production of original nano-composites with controlled properties.

Here, we focus as a case study on metal borate matrices containing as inclusions nanocrystals of metal–boron compounds, so-called metal borides. Borates have not been reported as nanostructured materials. In the bulk form, they show unique properties as boron sources,²⁵ glass modifiers,²⁵ Li-ion battery electrodes,²⁶ ionic conductors²⁷ and materials for non-linear optics.²⁵ Combining borates with nanoscaled

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†Electronic supplementary information (ESI) available: Experimental details, FTIR data, XPS, XRD and TEM characterization of a CaB₆/CaB₂O₄ nano-composite. See DOI: 10.1039/c8dt00932e

borides could bring some distinctive behaviors of boride nanocrystals: high electrical and thermal conductivity, hard/ soft magnetic properties, very high hardness and catalytic properties.^{28–31} HP conditions are among the most versatile methods^{25,27,32–36} used to synthesize borates with new crystal structures, unachievable at close-to-room pressure.^{37–45} Hence, HP-derived nanocomposites made of borate matrices and metal boride nano-inclusions should pave the way to a large range of new multifunctional materials.

In this work we propose a multidisciplinary approach merging nanomaterials chemistry with high pressure physics. We synthesize nanocrystals of metal borides, precipitated in inorganic molten salts,^{28,46–49} and then treat these nanoscaled precursors under high pressure conditions to trigger the crystallization of HP borate matrices around the nanocrystals. Both $\text{HfB}_2/\beta\text{-HfB}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{CaB}_6/\text{CaB}_2\text{O}_4(\text{iv})$ nanocomposites are discussed, as a proof-of-concept of this method.

Results and discussion

The nanoscaled precursors for subsequent HP–HT transformations consist of boride nanocrystals embedded in an amorphous boron-rich matrix. Their synthesis was performed by precipitation in the molten eutectic mixture $\text{LiCl} : \text{KCl}$, which can be heated up to 900 °C at room pressure.^{46,47} The resulting particles^{28,46} are surrounded by an amorphous matrix, which was shown^{28,46} to consist mainly of boron slightly oxidized from the exposure of powders to water and air during washing. To ensure evolution under HP–HT of the amorphous matrix toward borates and not boron polymorphs, the powders were exposed to air for 7 days to allow the oxidation of the boron matrix. Vibrations characteristic of the B–O bonds are evidenced at 1350 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra (ESI Fig. S1†).

The case-study of hafnium diboride HfB_2 is discussed first. XRD (Fig. 1) shows that HfB_2 is obtained as a pure crystalline

Fig. 1 XRD powder patterns of the initial HfB_2 -based precursor and of the $\text{HfB}_2/\text{HfB}_2\text{O}_5$ nanocomposite obtained after treatment at 5 GPa and 1200 °C. Le Bail refinements were performed according to HfB_2 and $\beta\text{-HfB}_2\text{O}_5$ structures with ICSD reference cards 30422 and 417031, respectively.

phase. The crystallite size is ca. 8 nm from the Scherrer formula. It is consistent with transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Fig. 2a), which exhibits 5 to 10 nm strongly contrasted nanocrystals with lattice fringes (FFT, Fig. 2a insert) indexed along the HfB_2 structure. The single-crystal particles are isotropic. This molten salt method is ideal to yield the smallest particle size reported for crystalline HfB_2 and other borides.²⁸ X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (Fig. S2 with detailed discussion in the ESI†) confirms that the matrix embedding the nanocrystals is made of oxidized boron, with characteristic B 1s peaks at 192.4 and 190.0 eV, in addition to the 186.6 eV peak typical of HfB_2 and 187.9 eV for elemental boron.⁵⁰ The nature of the matrix was also assessed by means of scanning transmission electron microscopy combined with high angle annular dark field detection (STEM-HAADF) for atomic number-contrast. The comparison of bright and dark field images (Fig. 2a and b) shows contrasted crystalline HfB_2 particles. The matrix is heterogeneous in brightness, with ca. 2 nm clusters contrasting (empty arrows in Fig. 2a and b) with the rest of the matrix. These bright areas highlight the presence of hafnium within the matrix. The thickness of the amorphous phase comprising hafnium clusters and amorphous oxidized boron is about 3 nm. Consequently, between two adjacent nanocrystals, a gap smaller than 10 nm is filled with oxidized amorphous boron doped with Hf atoms and clusters. The system is best described as a “nano-cookie”: the boride nanocrystals are included within the amorphous nano-

Fig. 2 TEM study of the nanoscaled hafnium-based precursor. (a) Bright field STEM image, insert: fast Fourier transform (FFT) of the squared zone on one nanocrystal, indexed on the HfB_2 structure (yellow: Hf atoms, gray: B atoms). (b) Corresponding STEM-HAADF Z-contrast image evidencing Hf-rich clusters. The empty arrows in (a) and (b) point at ca. 2 nm Hf-rich clusters. The scheme describing the initial material's nanocomposite structure according to XRD and TEM.

Fig. 3 HP-HT set-up: picture of a Paris-Edinburgh press and zoom (schematized) on the cell assembly. The sample is filled in the BN capsule. The diameter of the oven is initially 2 mm, 1.5 mm after HP-HT treatment.

structured matrix. Therefore, both components are nano-structured: the crystalline phase as nanoscale inclusions and the amorphous matrix made of nanoscale walls between the crystalline inclusions (Fig. 2).

The oxidized composite was placed in a large volume high pressure device (Fig. 3): a Paris-Edinburgh cell assembly, producing 1.5 mm diameter by 1–2 mm height pellets after HP-HT treatment. The sample was pressed at 5 GPa and heated to 1200 °C in 45 min, followed by a 90 min dwell time. After HP-HT treatment, the sample was quenched by cooling down to room temperature (ca. 1 min) and then slowly releasing the pressure over 12 h. The assembly was opened in air to recover the samples. For the hafnium-based system, the XRD pattern (Fig. 1) first shows that hafnium diboride is conserved upon HP-HT treatment. The Scherrer crystallite size evidences the preservation of the nanoscale although slight particle growth occurred, with the average size of 25 nm. XRD also indicates the crystallization of another phase identified as hafnium borate β -HfB₂O₅. This phase was first prepared by Knyrim and Huppertz from HfO₂ and B₂O₃ at 7.5 GPa and 1100 °C.⁴¹ To our knowledge, we provide in this report the second occurrence of this crystalline ternary hafnium borate, and the first case of nanostructured β -HfB₂O₅. Refined cell parameters of HfB₂ and β -HfB₂O₅ are close to the reported values: $a = b = 3.1457(4)$ Å, $c = 3.4733(6)$ Å for HfB₂ prior to the HP-HT treatment; $a = b = 3.1479(6)$ Å, $c = 3.4826(10)$ Å for HfB₂ and $a = 4.3904(7)$ Å, $b = 6.9137(10)$ Å, $c = 8.9953(17)$ Å, $\beta = 90.728(10)^\circ$ for HfB₂O₅ in the post-HP-HT sample.

STEM images (Fig. 4a and b) and particle size distributions (Fig. 4b insert) confirm the limited grain growth: the particle size does not exceed 30 nm after treatment at 1200 °C. The matrix is crystallized into β -HfB₂O₅ evidenced by characteristic lattice distances (Fig. 4c and d), in agreement with XRD. Thus, the amorphous matrix undergoes crystallization upon HP-HT. The interparticle gap is preserved (Fig. 4a, b and d), leading to nanostructured HfB₂/ β -HfB₂O₅ composite monoliths, which may be described again as “nano-cookies”: a crystalline

Fig. 4 TEM study of the HfB₂ nanocrystal-based nanocomposite obtained after HP-HT treatment: (a) bright field STEM image, (b) corresponding STEM-HAADF image with particle size distribution of the initial HfB₂ nanocrystals (light gray) and the HfB₂ nanocrystals observed after HP-HT treatment (dark gray). (c), (d) STEM images and the corresponding fast Fourier transforms indexed along the HfB₂ (blue) and β -HfB₂O₅ (white) structures (yellow: Hf atoms, red: BO₄ tetrahedra). The white arrow in (d) shows an interparticle gap.

Fig. 5 Scheme of the molten salt synthesis/high pressure-high temperature transformation approach toward new boron-based nanocomposites.

Fig. 6 TEM study of the CaB_6 nanocrystal-based nanocomposite before (a and the corresponding scheme with CaB_6 structure (blue: Ca atom, gray: B_6 octahedra)) and after HP-HT crystallization (b, c and the corresponding scheme with $\text{CaB}_2\text{O}_4(\text{IV})$ structure (blue: Ca atoms, green: BO_4 tetrahedra)): (a) TEM image of the initial CaB_6 -amorphous matrix composite, (b) TEM image and (c) Fourier-filtered image of an HRTEM micrograph high-light the good crystallinity of the crystalline $\text{CaB}_2\text{O}_4(\text{IV})$ matrix.

β - HfB_2O_5 matrix embedding nano-inclusions of HfB_2 and containing nanoscaled walls separating the inclusions. The matrix thus remains confined between these inclusions.

The overall evolution of the sample and the synthesis approach are schematized in Fig. 5. The HP-HT treatment pre-presents the metal boride nanocrystals with limited grain growth, while the treatment mostly affects the matrix that crystallizes into a rare borate phase but keeps its structuration around the nanocrystals. Remarkably, up to now only scarce reports have described the synthesis of nanostructured inorganic materials under HP-HT conditions.^{11–14,51} Indeed, such treatments usually yield reduced interfaces by large crystal growth. Our striking result arises from two kinetic factors. First, high pressure limits atomic diffusion,⁵² thus increasing the activation barrier necessary for grain growth. Second, high pressure is also likely to restrain particle migration within the matrix they are embedded in. In the case-study shown here, hafnium atoms initially present in the amorphous boron-rich matrix yield the crystallization of β - HfB_2O_5 upon HP-HT treatment.

To demonstrate the generalization of the approach, we have explored another boride/borate system, relying on CaB_6 nanocrystals (ESI† and Fig. 6). The initial ~ 15 nm crystalline nanoparticles embedded in an amorphous boron-rich matrix (Fig. 6 and Fig. S3†) have been prepared in molten salts.⁴⁶ After the HP-HT treatment (5 GPa, 1200 °C), the CaB_6 nanocrystals have only slightly grown, with the diameter maintained below 30 nm (Fig. S4†). The matrix crystallized into the $\text{CaB}_2\text{O}_4(\text{IV})$ phase (Fig. 6 and Fig. S3, S4†) which was reported only once⁵³ and as a bulk material. Again, we report the first occurrence of a nanostructured material based on this high pressure phase, as well as the first nanocomposite with such an HP solid as the matrix.

Conclusions

To conclude, we have shown the original combination of chemically-derived metal boride nanocrystals with HP-HT treatments to prepare innovative nanocomposites by high pressure crystallization of ternary borates. Nanostructuration is preserved upon crystallization of the matrix under extreme HP conditions, with the size of the nano-inclusions not exceeding 30 nm at a pressure as high as 5 GPa. These results validate this new approach combining the solution-phase synthesis of inorganic nanomaterials and high pressure to yield nanocomposites made of phases not reachable under ambient conditions. Particularly, the method benefits from the ability of molten salt synthesis to prepare single-phase metal boride nanocrystals in order to achieve nanocomposites well controlled from the compositional viewpoint.^{28,46,47,54} The resulting materials establish a new family of heterostructures built on HP solids. They provide an intimate combination of metal-lic (HfB_2) or insulating (CaB_6) nano-inclusions with rare insulating ceramic compounds. This approach paves the way to advanced mechanical, electrical, thermal and optical properties.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

Acknowledgements

Christophe Calers from the Centre of Institute of Materials of Paris Centre is acknowledged for XPS measurements. The

authors thank the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique its Energy Unit and French state funds managed by the ANR within the Investissements d'Avenir programme ANR-11-IDEX-0004-02, more specifically within the Cluster of Excellence MATISSE, for funding. The Agence Nationale de la Recherche (project ANR-2011-BS08-018), Sorbonne Universités-UPMC, Collège de France and the METSA (Microscopie Electronique et Sonde Atomique) network are also acknowledged for financial support.

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